

DELIVERABLE D7.2

CURRICULUM SUMMER SCHOOL

WP7 – Training

Lead Beneficiary: INFARMED

WP Leader and Institution: Irena Mlinaric-Rascan (UL)

Contributing Partner(s): UL, INFARMED, EATRIS

Contractual Delivery Date: 30/06/2021 extended to 31/08/2021

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EATRIS-Plus is a flagship project aiming to consolidate our infrastructure's capacities in the field of personalised medicine (PM). One of our aims is to promote and expand our training opportunities and deliver new educational events and content to better serve our research community.

Task 7.3 foresees the delivery of three iterations of Summer School of Translational Medicine (TM) that focus on how translational medicine can be used for Personalised Medicine applications.

The development process of the curriculum for the Summer School was led by partner INFARMED (Claudia Faria), together with the assistance of members from UL – the WP7 leader (Irena-Mlinaric-Rascan), the partner representatives from the scientific WPs (WPs 1,2 and 3) from RUMC, UH/FIMM and SERMAS, as well as EATRIS Coordination and Support Office.

The curriculum was designed over a six-month period in late 2020/ early 2021 and eventually adapted to a virtual setting due to the pandemic.

The planned 5-day program had to be adapted considering the new virtual format. It was decided to hold it in 5 mornings, maintaining the principles of content, but allowing for more flexibility in schedule. Due to the global COVID-19 pandemic and the related challenges the event was postponed from April 2021 to take place on 14-18 June 2021.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Our flagship project EATRIS-Plus aims to build further capabilities and deliver innovative scientific tools to support the long-term sustainability strategy of EATRIS as one of Europe's key research infrastructures for PM.

The project spans 4 years (2020-2023), the consortium consists of 19 partners and the total budget is 4,9 mil euros. Activities are divided into 9 WPs overseen by the Steering Committee consisting of each WP leader.

The main goals of the EATRIS-Plus project will be to:

- Consolidate EATRIS capacities in the field of PM (particularly omics technologies) to better serve academia and industry and augment the number of EATRIS Innovation Hubs with large pharma;
- Drive patient empowerment through active involvement in the infrastructure's operations;
- Expand strategic partnerships with research infrastructures and other relevant stakeholders; and
- Further strengthen the long-term sustainability of the EATRIS financial model.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

Since 2016, EATRIS has been organising a yearly five-day training course for the next generation of scientists (PhD students, Post-Docs) on translational medicine (TMex: Translational Medicine

Explained). Initially funded by Erasmus-Plus, the course is now owned by EATRIS and made sustainable through collaboration with EATRIS Spain (VHIR) and Spanish private funder La Caixa foundation, and a reasonable fee requested from the students.

Task 7.3 supports the development and delivery of a similar face-to-face programme for senior academics, healthcare providers and industry focusing on more advanced aspects of translational medicine, and how translational research can be used for PM applications. The aim of the proposed activity is also to be inclusive and to engage the participants from lower research and innovation performing countries.

The organisation of the course is led by consortium partner INFARMED and the 5-day event was expected to take place in person in Lisbon, Portugal annually from 2021-2023 (three iterations).

It was initially proposed that the face-to-face programme would reach 40 participants by edition.

The curricula and the format of the Summer School was based on a survey performed within EATRIS community (D7.1.), with the aim to identify the most relevant and timely topics as well as the preferred delivery format (in-person or virtual) and duration (2-3 day course or 5-day course).

The results of the survey proved a vast demand for training in personalised medicine covering the contemporary methodological approaches (- omic technologies, data analyses) as well as regulatory aspect of biomarker validation and approval, as well as engagement of patients and wider public in the process of personalized medicine approach.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

The development process of the curriculum for the Summer School was led by partner INFARMED (EATRIS Portugal) and Claudia Faria, together with the assistance of members from UL, the WP7 leader Irena-Mlinaric-Rascan, the partner representatives from the scientific WPs (WPs 1,2 and 3) from RUMC, FIMM and SERMAS, as well as EATRIS-ERIC.

The curriculum was designed over a six-month period in late 2020 to early 2021 and eventually adapted to a virtual setting due to the pandemic.

The EATRIS-Plus Summer School in PM was held from 14-18 June 2021. The entire event was held virtually (via Webex Cisco system) in the mornings from 10 am until 1pm CET to allow for maximum flexibility for participants. The curriculum addressed key topics linked to PM including omics-based strategies, biomarkers, patient stratification, electronic health records, data access and sharing, machine learning and Artificial Intelligence, quality and reproducibility, animal and non-animal models, and patient engagement.

Renown experts and scientists were invited as speakers reflecting a high level and timely transfer of knowledge to the Summer School participants.

The goal of this first Summer School was to give an overview on the most relevant topics in PM. To that end the programme started with omics-based strategies (patient stratification, biomarker signatures), went through the structural pillars of PM, and moved to preclinical studies (quality and

reproducibility, intellectual property, good laboratory practices), including sessions on animal and non-animal preclinical studies.

The last two days of the Summer School were dedicated to clinical trials and biomarker validation, highlighting the crucial role of patient engagement and advocacy. And a special session on Patient Engagement was held led by project partner EPF (The European Patients' Forum) in the afternoon of the 4th day of the Summer School.

Finally, the regulatory aspects of PM and its impact in PM were discussed. To encourage interaction with the participants of the course, time was given for discussion in the end of each session.

Furthermore, two round tables were included on clinical trials and regulatory aspects of personalised medicine, with experts in those fields.

Special consideration was made to attract participants from the lower research and innovation performing countries, and nearly 30% of the total registrants were from countries with such designation. Summer School was well attended by all EATRIS-Plus project partners, national nodes as well as researchers from many other EATRIS institutions. The feedback to the first iteration of the Summer School was overwhelmingly positive with 53 respondents giving the average score of 4.26 out of 5 points. 83% of the respondents said that the amount of information in the curriculum was "just right". Cumulative 91% of the respondents stated that this course is "somewhat likely" or "highly likely" to have an impact on their career/ research plans, and nearly all the respondents (96%) said that they will recommend this course to their peers.

NEXT STEPS

The next editions of the EATRIS-Plus Summer School will be held in April 2022 and April 2023. It is expected that they will take place in-person at INFARMED premises in Lisbon, Portugal.

Since the first Summer School was an overview on several topics related to PM, for the next courses it is planned to go deeper into some key topics in PM including omics technologies (proteomics, metabolomics and pharmacogenomics), biomarkers (development and technology transfer path), artificial intelligence in the development of biomarkers and clinical trials, and medicines development.

To foster interaction between participants and the faculty of the Summer School it is also planned to include case presentations and discussions.

A site visit to a local research institute, infrastructure (Biobank) or industry, will also be included in the programme for the face-to-face editions.

ABBREVIATIONS

TM – translational medicine

PM – personalised medicine

EPF – The European Patients' Forum

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The project manager requested for an extension of this deliverable (original due date 30/06) until 31/08. The deliverable was granted an extension by the project officer on 15/06.

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

n/a

APPENDICES

Appendix 1 – EATRIS-Plus Summer School Program 2021 (Virtual)

EATRIS-Plus Summer School in Personalised Medicine

14-18 June 2021

eatris+

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871096

Our flagship project **eatris+** aims to build further capabilities and deliver innovative scientific tools to support the long-term sustainability strategy of EATRIS as one of Europe's key European research infrastructures for Personalised Medicine.

Organised by:

*University of Ljubljana
Faculty of Pharmacy*

eatris

European infrastructure
for translational medicine

Programme

14 June

Day 1

Opening remarks

from Toni Andreu, Claudia Faria, Irena Mlinaric and Rui Santos Ivo

10.00-10.15

Introduction to Personalised Medicine

Chair: Toni Andreu

Personalised Medicine

Biomarker discovery and development

Omics in translational and clinical application

Alain van Gool

Peter Groenen

Laura Bermejo

10.15-11.45

10.15-10.45

10.45-11.15

11.15-11.45

Coffee break

11.45-12.00

Omics-based strategies in PM II

Chair: Astrid Vicente

Patient stratification and omics

biomarker signatures

Challenges in the analysis of omics data for PM

José Carlos Machado

Peter-Bram t'Hoen

12.00-13.00

12.00-12.30

12.30-13.00

Programme

15 June

Day 2

Structural pillars of PM

Chair: Andre Albergaria

Biobanks

Harmonized clinical data

(EHR – Electronic Health Records)

Data sources / Data access and sharing

(Data protection)

Jens Habermann

Steve Canham

Deepak Unni

10.00-11.30

10.00-10.30

10.30-11.00

11.00-11.30

Coffee break

11.30-12.00

Communication & Information

Chair: Toni Andreu

Healthcare technology solutions in PM

Machine learning and Artificial Intelligence

Alfonso Valencia

Marinka Zitnik

12.00-13.00

12.00-12.30

12.30-13.00

Programme 16 June Day 3

Pre-Clinical Studies in Personalised Medicine

10.00-11.30

Chair: Irena Mlinaric

Quality and reproducibility

Ivo Gut

10.00-10.30

Intellectual property

Tim Moser

10.30-11.00

Good Laboratory Practices

Ana Claudia Figueiredo

11.00-11.30

GLP-requirements for Pre-Clinical studies

Coffee break

11.30-12.00

Pre-Clinical models

12.00-13.00

Chair: Emanuela Oldoni

Animal models (xenografts, PDXs)

Vibeke Fosse

12.00-12.30

Non- animal models (biomimetics, organoids)

Evangelos Daskalopoulos

12.30-13.00

Programme 17 June Day 4

Biomarkers II (Clinical)

Chair: Claudia Faria

Clinical validation

Santiago Pérez Hoyos

10.00-10.30

Biomarker-based clinical trials

Julio Oliveira

10.30-11.00

Patient engagement

Merete Schmiegelow (EATRIS+ PAC)

11.00-11.30

Coffee break

11.30-12.00

ROUND TABLE: Clinical Trials In the era of PM

12.00-13.00

Moderator: Julio Oliveira + Speakers from morning sessions, and Fatima Vaz – CEIC, Portugal

Patient Engagement Satellite Session

14.00-15.30

Speakers: Valentina Strammiello, Hannes Jarke, Oriana Sousa and Michela Onali

Programme 18 June Day 5

Regulatory aspects of PM

Chair: Dinah Duarte

Regulatory aspects of PM

The impact of PM in Health Care industry

Health Economics/reimbursement policy

Maria Isabel Vieira

Antoine Bril

Umberto Restelli

10.00-11.30

10.00-10.30

10.30-11.00

11.00-11.30

Coffee break

11.30-11.45

ROUND TABLE: Regulatory aspects and PM adoption in Health Care Systems

Moderator: Maria do Céu Machado + Speakers and the Chair from morning sessions

11.45-12.30

Closing remarks

from Toni Andreu, Claudia Faria and Irena Mlinaric

12.30-13.00

Meet the speakers

Take a look...

... and read more about speakers at the EATRIS-Plus Summer School in Personalised Medicine. Read their introductions and get to know them before the beginning of the Summer School.

Rui S. Ivo

President of INFARMED, I.P., National Authority of Medicines and Healthcare Products Governor EATRIS PT

Rui Santos Ivo is the President of INFARMED since June 2019 and a member of the Management Board of the EMA and the Executive Board of EUnetHTA. He is the Vice-chair of the Valletta Permanent Technical Committee/Valletta Declaration. He is also an Invited Assistant Professor of Medicines Regulation, at the Faculty of Pharmacy of the University of Lisbon. He is an external elected member of the General Council of the University of Coimbra. Previously he was President (2014/2016) and Vice-President (2011/2014) of the Central Administration of the Health System (ACSS,IP) at the Ministry of Health, in Portugal. He was Coordinator of the Hospital Reform Project Team (2012/2015) and chaired the Governance College for the Public Health Subsystems (2015/2016). R. S. Ivo started his professional career as a hospital pharmacist at Hospital de Egas Moniz, in Lisbon. In 1993 he joined INFARMED, where he held various responsibilities, like Vice-president (1994-2000; 2016-2019) and President (2002-2005). In 2000/2002 he worked as Administrator at the Directorate of the European Medicines Agency and in 2006/2008 he worked for the European Commission as Administrator at the Pharmaceuticals Unit, Directorate General for Enterprise and Industry. He was the first Chairman of the European Union Heads of Medicines Agencies Management Group (2004-2005). His awards include: Imofariz Prize, Personality of the Year in the Pharmaceutical Sector (2004), European Correspondent Member, Académie Nationale de Pharmacie, France (2014) and Medal (gold) for distinguished Services, Ministry of Health (2015).

Toni Andreu

M.D. Ph.D

Toni is specialised in genetics and genomics of rare diseases. He has been working in the field of neuromuscular disorders from the translational perspective of the pipeline, from basic science to the development of cell and animal models and clinical research.

After working in Columbia University in New York on mitochondrial disorders from 1998 to 2001, he moved to Barcelona to create the Neuromuscular Lab at the Vall d'Hebron Research Institute where he became Director of the Neurosciences Research Program.

He has also been extremely active in the field of policy-making and held positions as the Director of the Spanish National Institute of Health Carlos III, creating the national program for personalised medicine. He has also been the CEO of the Bellvitge Hospital, one of the most important University hospitals in Spain, as well as the Director General for Research and Innovation at the Catalan Ministry of Health.

Toni is now the Scientific Director at EATRIS, the European Advanced Infrastructure for Translational Research.

Claudia Faria

Prof. M.D. Ph.D

Claudia Faria received her MD from the University of Coimbra in 2001. She did her training in the Department of Neurosurgery at Hospital de Santa Maria – Centro Hospitalar Universitário Lisboa Norte and became a board-certified neurosurgeon in 2010. With her interest in the genetics of brain tumours, particularly in the paediatric population, she did her PhD at the Arthur and Sonia Labatt Brain Tumour Research Centre, The Hospital for Sick Children (Canada) with Prof Rutka. Using the genetic signatures of medulloblastoma, she studied the mechanisms of tumour recurrence and dissemination and identified novel small molecule inhibitors that were successfully tested in preclinical models of the disease. Upon returning to Lisbon in 2014, Claudia Faria became a clinician-scientist working as a Consultant Neurosurgeon at CHULN, as a researcher at Instituto de Medicina Molecular João Lobo Antunes and as an Invited Assistant Professor of Neurosurgery and Neurology at Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa. She founded the Brain Tumor Bank at Biobanco-iMM in 2012 and became co-director of Biobanco-iMM in 2018, being responsible to supervise and coordinate the activities of scientific and technical committees, to foster the collaboration between medical doctors and researchers and to promote dissemination and fundraising actions for scientific research. Since 2018 she is the Portuguese representative in the Board of National Directors of EATRIS and in November 2020 she was elected chair of the Board of National Directors.

Irena Mlinarič-Raščan

Prof. Ph.D. MPharm.

Prof. dr. Irena Mlinarič-Raščan, MPharm, is the dean of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University Ljubljana, Slovenia, National director of EATRIS Slovenia and President of the UNESCO National Committee. She is a full professor in pharmacogenomics, immunology and cell biology. Irena completed two postdoctoral fellowships at the Mount Sinai Hospital Toronto and at the Tokyo University, and was a guest professor at the Universities of Bern and Vienna. Her research work involves pharmacogenomics approaches in individualisation of leukaemia and lymphoma therapies, focusing on thiopurine personalized therapy, identification of novel target molecules including prostaglandin receptor 4, proteasome and immunoproteasome, which further serve for lead design and optimisation.

Alain van Gool

Prof. Ph.D

Alain van Gool is professor Personalised Healthcare and heads the Translational Metabolic Laboratory at the Radboud University Medical Centre, with a strong passion in the application of biomarkers in translational medicine and personalised healthcare. His professional background since 1991 is a mix of academia, pharmaceutical industry, applied research institutes, university medical centers. He has been leading technology-based biomarker laboratories, cross-functional expert teams, therapeutic project teams and public-private consortia, many of which were focused on the discovery, development and implementation of translational biomarkers in a variety of therapeutic areas. His technical expertise resides most strongly in molecular profiling (various Omics approaches), analytical biomarker development, and applications in translational scientific research.

Alain currently heads the 100 fte Translational Metabolic Laboratory of the Radboudumc, a mixed function research-diagnostic lab that specialises in genetic metabolic disorders and includes the proteomics, glycomics & metabolomics platforms. He also coordinates the Radboudumc Technology Centers, is Scientific Lead Technologies of DTL (the Dutch Techcenter for Life Sciences), is co-initiator of Health-RI (the Netherlands Personalised Medicine and Health Research Infrastructure), is PI of the Biomarker Development Center and is chair Biomarker Platform of EATRIS thus contributing to the organisation and coordination of local, national and European technology infrastructures.

Peter Groenen

Ph.D

Peter Groenen currently heads the Translational Biomarker Group at Idorsia Pharmaceuticals. Holding a PhD in molecular genetics he is interested in the molecular aspects of disease and treatment. He received his MSc in Biochemistry and Physiology from the Radboud University, the Netherlands.

Before obtaining his PhD in biomedical sciences at the Center for Human Genetics at the Gasthuisberg Medical Hospital, University of Leuven, Belgium he was a junior scientist at the National Institute for Health and Environmental Protection, the Netherlands and F. Hoffmann-La Roche AG, Switzerland. Peter held several positions with increasing responsibility at Organon NV (part of Akzo Nobel), Schering-Plough and Merck Sharp & Dohme, the Netherlands.

Peter Groenen has authored or co-authored over 50 peer reviewed articles in diverse areas of genetics, bioinformatics and biomarkers. He led two large national public private partnership projects in the Netherlands on genomics in psychiatric disorders and bioinformatics.

He currently also serves as an editor of the recently launched journal “Digital Biomarkers” and serves as a core member of the DayOne initiative of the BaselArea.Swiss.

Laura García Bermejo

Ph.D

M. Laura García Bermejo has a PhD in Biology (UAH-CIB, CSIC). She is a Senior Researcher at Ramon y Cajal Research Institute, with category A and since 2006, Head of the group Biomarkers and Therapeutic Targets. Her group has a translational and multidisciplinary character and includes basic and clinical researchers. She is also the Director of the Core Facility: Biomarkers and Therapeutic Target Unit, included in the IRYCIS Services Portfolio, since December 2014. In addition, Laura is co-chair of the Biomarkers Platform of EATRIS. Over the last 10 years, Laura has worked on the study of pathophysiological mechanisms responsible for nephropathies, cancer, cardiovascular diseases and infectious diseases, establishing new in vitro and in vivo models that reproduce the clinical context.

She is currently working on the identification and validation of new biomarkers and therapeutic targets based on miRNAs and long-ncRNAs, in different pathologies. It has generated 11 patents, already granted in Spain, Europe, Mexico, China and others in PCT extension.

The entrepreneurial profile of Laura is complemented by the award of a FIPSE grant, the CAM Health Start program, and also the Caixa Impulse 2017 program. Since 2006, when she became Group Leader, she has been Principal Investigator of 24 projects: international and national, collaborator in 31 other projects.

Astrid Vicente

Ph.D.

Astrid Vicente is senior researcher, head of the Department of Health Promotion and Non-communicable Disease Prevention at the Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, in Lisbon Portugal, and invited Associate Professor at Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa. She is an elected vice-chair for ICPeMed (International Consortium for Personalised Medicine) since 2017, and is the representative from the Portuguese Ministry of Health at the European 1+Million Genomes Initiative, where she is part of the Coordination Team. Astrid Vicente is also coordinating the effort to develop a strategy for Genomic Medicine in Portugal.

Astrid's research focuses on understanding the etiology and biological processes underlying complex noncommunicable diseases, with a particular interest in pathologies of the nervous system, like Autism Spectrum Disorder and other neuropsychiatric disorders. Astrid is interested in a broad perspective of interactions between genetic and environmental factors to clarify the origins of multifactorial disorders, and promote progress towards translation of knowledge into personalised strategies for medical care and prevention. She holds a degree in biochemistry, and a PhD in molecular biology from Universidade de Coimbra (1996).

José C. Machado

Ph.D

José C. Machado (JCM) is Associate Professor in the Faculty of Medicine of Porto, vice-president of the Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology of the University of Porto (Ipatimup), and Coordinator of the Cancer Program at i3S. He studied Biology at the University of Porto and developed his PhD in the Universities of Tübingen, Germany and Porto, Portugal. The scientific question that drives JCM's research group is how genetically encoded information in cancer cells is shared among the diverse cellular constituents of a tumour, and how that affects the heterogeneity and plasticity of cancer cells. JCM has been awarded research projects by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), by the Portuguese Agency for Innovation (ADI), by the Portuguese Ministry of Health, by Worldwide Cancer Research and by the European Union. JCM is also the head of R&D at the molecular genetics laboratory of the IPATIMUP Diagnostics Unit. This is one of the reference laboratories in Portugal for the detection of cancer biomarkers, genetic diagnosis of hereditary cancer syndromes and pathology. As of April 2021, JCM (Scopus Author ID 7102792651) co-authors 166 publications in indexed journals with IF, with 11530 total citations, and with an h-index of 44.

Peter-Bram t'Hoen

Prof. Ph.D.

Prof.dr. Peter-Bram 't Hoen obtained his Master degrees in Biochemistry and Pharmacochimistry cum laude from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. In 2002, he received his PhD from Leiden University. In 2002-2009, he was postdoctoral researcher in Leiden University Medical Center's department of Human Genetics, investigating disease mechanisms, biomarkers and antisense therapies for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy. In 2010-2018 he headed the Bioinformatics research group in the same department, as an assistant and associate professor, focusing on the analysis and integration of high-dimensional molecular data. In 2018 he started as full professor of Bioinformatics at Radboud University Medical Center and head of the Centre for Molecular and Biomolecular Informatics (CMBI). In this position, he is dedicated to the advancement of personalised medicine approaches by integrative use of -omics and clinical data. 't Hoen leads the data analysis, integration and stewardship pillar in X-omics, one of the large national research infrastructures. 't Hoen is actively contributing to national infrastructures such as HealthRI, BBMRI-NL and DTL, and international infrastructures such as European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases, EATRIS and ELIXIR. He is also co-leading the Personal Health Train coalition, developing a data infrastructure to advance healthcare and biomedical science through interoperable and federated data management. He has published >200 papers in scientific journals.

Andre Albergaria

Prof. Ph.D

André Albergaria is a researcher specialised in Oncobiology. His scientific expertise is focused on epigenetic regulatory mechanisms in breast cancer, cancer therapy resistance, and on biomarker discovery and validation. André holds a PhD from the Institute of Health and Life Sciences from University of Minho and was a PhD resident at the Imperial College School of Medicine of London. André has a Post-Graduation in BioBusiness, from AMC Graduate School and Amsterdam BioMed Cluster, and worked as an Investment Consultant in the LifeSciences & MedTech Team of the company Portugal Ventures. Over the last 20 years of scientific career, Albergaria has published more than 33 papers in international peer-reviewed journals. Albergaria is a professor at the Faculty of Medicine of University of Porto and is the coordinator of the i3S Translational Research and Industry Partnerships Office (Research and Innovation Unit), a group that work on the interface between the health care/pharma industry, clinicians and academic research teams. Albergaria is member of the Portuguese Coordination of the Research & Innovation Agenda on Health and Clinical and Translational Research. He is a project evaluator for several public and private entities, including pharma companies, and is an expert member of the H2020 SC1 Programme Committee, an health expert at Perin – Portugal in Europe Research and Innovation Network and developed and contributed as scientific expert to several European Organisations/Consortium such as ICPeMed.

Jens Habermann

Prof. M.D. Ph.D

Professor Jens K. Habermann, MD PhD, is Director General of BBMRI-ERIC (Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium) since September 2020. He is on leave of absence from the University of Lübeck as Head of the Section of Translational Surgical Oncology and Biobanking and as Head of ICB-L (Interdisciplinary Center for Biobanking-Lübeck). He obtained his MD training at the Medical University of Lübeck (Lübeck, Germany), received his PhD at the Cancer Center Karolinska, Karolinska Institute (Stockholm, Sweden) and a Postdoctoral Fellowship at the National Cancer Institute, NIH (Bethesda, USA). As board certified specialist in human genetics, Jens combines clinics, biobanking, and translational (cancer) research to optimise precision medicine.

Steve Canham

M.Sc.

Steve Canham is Data Project Manager at European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN). Steve had his own business for almost 10 years providing a variety of short and medium term contract work in clinical trials IT throughout Europe. He has 9 years of experience developing and managing systems and leading a team of developers within the Institute of Cancer Research's Clinical Trials and Statistics Unit.

Deepak Unni

M.Sc.

Deepak Unni is a Bioinformatician by training and a Software Developer by experience. He is passionate about working at the interface of Bioinformatics and Data Science to support translational informatics. Deepak is also keen about knowledge representation and semantics, and using principles from semantic web technologies to build intelligent systems that can realise the dream of precision medicine.

Currently, Deepak is working at the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) in Heidelberg as part of the Korb group where most of his time is dedicated to the German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA). As part of the consortium, he is involved in coordinating the frontend and backend development of GHGA. Deepak is also involved in addressing the metadata challenges in GHGA, and collaborate with other stakeholders to support existing and new data types and modalities in GHGA.

Alfonso Valencia

Prof. Ph.D

Prof. Alfonso Valencia is ICREA research Professor, Director of the Life Sciences Department of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, and Director of the Spanish National Bioinformatics Institute INB-ELIXIR-ES. His research interest is the development of Computational Biology methods and their application to biomedical problems. Some of the computational methods he developed are considered pioneering work in areas such as biological text mining, protein coevolution and more recently epigenetic and disease networks. He participates in some of the key cancer related international consortia. In terms of community services, he is one of the initial promoters of what is now the ELIXIR infrastructure, founder of the Spanish Bioinformatics network and founder member and former president of ISCB the professional association of Bioinformaticians and the Executive Editor of the main journal in the field - Bioinformatics OUP.

Marinka Zitnik

Prof. Ph.D

Marinka Zitnik is an Assistant Professor at Harvard University with appointments in the Department of Biomedical Informatics, Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, and Harvard Data Science. Marinka is a computer scientist studying machine learning, focusing on network medicine, the fusion of biomedical research and patient data, and the development of safer and more effective medicines. Before Harvard, she was a postdoctoral fellow in Computer Science at Stanford. Marinka has published extensively in top machine learning venues and leading biomedical journals. Her algorithms are used by major institutions, including Baylor College of Medicine, Karolinska Institute, Stanford Medical School, Massachusetts General Hospital, and the pharmaceutical industry. Her research won several best paper and research awards from the International Society for Computational Biology, Bayer Early Excellence in Science Award, Amazon Research Faculty Award, and two Rising Star Awards from MIT Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (EECS) and The Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, being the only young scientist who received such recognition in both EECS and Biomedicine.

Ivo Gut

Ph.D

Ivo is Director of the Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico (CNAG-CRG), one of the largest genome sequencing center in Europe. From 1999 to 2009 he established, at the Centre National de Génotypage (CNG), the highest throughput genotyping platform in Europe, where he executed many genome-wide association studies and was the coordinator of the EU-funded Project READNA in which 2nd, 3rd and 4th generation nucleic acid analysis technologies were developed. At CNAG, he leads the Biomedical Genomics Group, he is principal investigator of the ongoing EU-funded projects Beyond 1M Genomes, 3TR , BCLL@las, EUCanCan, SPIDIA4P, EJP RD, and was coordinator of RD-Connect (part of the International Rare Disease Research Consortium) which tackle important health issues. Currently, he coordinates EASI-Genomics, an EU Infrastructure Project. He is very active in large international projects and consortia such as the International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC), the International Human Genome Consortium (IHEC), and the International Rare Disease Research Consortium (IRDiRC). He is author of more than 400 research papers, 11 reviews and 12 book chapters, cited over 49 000 times, inventor of 26 patents or patent applications, founder of 4 biotech start-ups, and serves on numerous international advisory boards.

Tim Moser

M.Sc. MBA.

Tim has a track record in intellectual property, technology transfer, and biotech business development and industry partnering in the USA and Europe. He was business development director Vrije Universiteit Medical Center Industry Alliance Office in Amsterdam, leading industry partnering at EATRIS and currently works at Knowledge Transfer & Contracting of the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI).

Ana Claudia Figueiredo

Ph.D.

Ana has a BSc in Biology by the University of Lisbon and MSc in Immunology and PhD in Biomedical Sciences (Immunology) by the University of Oporto. Studies in Immunology specially focused on autoimmunity and immunological tolerance and on development of T cells.

She is an assessor of non-clinical studies for human medicines at the Portuguese Regulatory Agency for Human Medicines and Health Products for more than 20 years. Ana has experience with assessment in the context of clinical trial and marketing authorisation applications, submitted through different types of procedures (national, decentralised/mutual recognition and centralised), and of scientific advices. Ana also has experience with assessment of different types of medicines, for instance, small chemical molecules and biological medicines products.

Emanuela Oldoni

Ph.D

Emanuela is an enthusiastic scientist with passion for new challenges. She is mainly interested in translational medicine because it permits a continuous exchange between clinic and laboratory aspects.

She got her PhD in Molecular and Translational Medicine in 2018, at University of Milan, leading a project about biomarkers in neurodegenerative diseases, where she applied different methodologies and multi-omics approaches. Later, she obtained a prestigious post-doc research fellowship, funded by ECTRIMS, on biomarkers and genetics in multiple sclerosis providing a rationale for personalised medicine. After five productive years as researcher at various academic laboratories in Italy and Belgium, she has been working as Scientific Programme Manager at EATRIS since January 2020. At EATRIS she combines her strong scientific background and her soft skills to facilitate industry-academic collaborations pursuing a common aim: innovation and improvement of human life.

Vibeke Fosse

M.Sc.

Vibeke Fosse is a veterinary surgeon who holds a Master degree specialisation in companion animal oncology. Since 2016 she has been working with preclinical oncology research at the University of Bergen in Professor Emmet Mc Cormacks' research group, focusing on developing clinically relevant animal models for translation.

Evangelos Daskalopoulos

Ph.D MPharm

Evangelos (aka Vangelis) Daskalopoulos obtained his MPharm/Pharmacy degree with First Class Honours at the University of Brighton (UK) in 2005. After receiving training in hospital pharmacy (NHS) he completed his PhD thesis (2012) in Pharmacology and Drug Metabolism at the Medical School of the University of Ioannina, Greece. Later on, he received ample experience in basic cardiovascular research by working as a post-doctoral fellow in Maastricht University (Maastricht, The Netherlands) and UCLouvain (Brussels, Belgium). In October 2020, he joined the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the European Commission's science and knowledge hub, located in Ispra, Italy. There, he is working as a Technical / Scientific Officer for the F.3 Unit, supporting the Unit's activities on promoting alternatives to animal testing and safety assessment of chemicals, with a special interest on ATMPs.

Santiago Pérez Hoyos

Ph.D

Santiago has a Bachelor in Mathematics (Statistics), PhD in Public Health. He is the Head of the Statistics and Bioinformatics Unit at Vall d'Hebrón Research Institute(VHIR). He is also an adjunct lecturer of department of genetics, microbiology and Statistics at University of Barcelona. More than 30 years of experience in the field of consulting and data analysis in health sciences, organising and participating in postgraduate training activities in statistics and public health institutions and universities.

Santiago has experience as a researcher in competitive projects at national and international level, collaborating during several years with the most recognised statisticians and epidemiologist in HIV Cohort studies (Cascade, MR-UK) HIVCausal (Harvard Public Health School), Cohere (UE, Eurocord). Santiago currently collaborates with several research groups on the campus that include modelling and biomarkers validation. He is a member of the EU-PEARL project of Clinical Trials Platforms.

Julio Oliveira

M.D. Ph.D

Julio Oliveira (JO) concluded his graduation in Medicine at the Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas de Abel Salazar – Porto University (ICBAS-UP), in 2003. Since April 2011 he is Medical Oncologist at IPO Porto. In April 2017 he obtained the specialty of Clinical Pharmacology. At present time he is developing a PhD project in the area of Immuno-Oncology (ICBAS-UP). JO is vice-president of Associação Portuguesa de Investigação em Cancro (ASPIC), presidente of fiscal board of Sociedade Portuguesa de Oncologia (SPO) and board director of Grupo de Estudos Oncológicos (GEOS).

Since 2019 JO is the head of Early Phase Clinical Trials Unit of IPO Porto (EPCTU-IPOP). He was Principal Investigator (PI) responsible for several phase I-III clinical trials in breast and lung cancer, phase I clinical trials in solid tumors, translational research projects focusing on cancer biomarkers and responsible for the development of the institutional Precision Oncology Program. Also as PI, he is developing a phase Ib/II investigator initiated clinical trial aiming to study the role of neoadjuvant immune checkpoint inhibitors in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). As co-investigator, JO is developing the phase I clinical trial, first-in-human, with the first cancer treatment developed in Portugal, the Redaporfin.

Fátima Vaz

M.Sc.

Fatima is a Senior Medical Oncologist with extensive clinical experience in General Oncology and research experience on Breast, Gynecological and Hereditary Cancer. She has a Master of Science (Faculty of Medicine, Katholieke University Leuven), with a thesis on research sponsored by direct to consumer genetics companies.

Fatima is a member of the Executive Committee of the Portuguese Central Research Ethics Committee (CEIC) and the local Ethics Committee of the Portuguese Cancer Institute in Lisbon.

On the regulatory level, Fatima has several years of experience in elaborating reports concerning reimbursement of Health Technologies. She has a post-graduate in Health Management (Catholic University Business School, Lisbon).

Merete Schmiegelow

Ph.D

Merete is educated at University level (pharmaceutical and medical) and appointed as Honorary Ambassador in Regulatory Science at the University of Copenhagen including developing a Master Degree in Regulatory Science. She has many years international, industrial experience at various managerial positions throughout the medicines R&D, approval and life cycle.

Retired from the pharmaceutical industry by 1 July 2017, to concentrate her focus on patient engagement activities:

- EUPATI EU Executive Committee, EUPATI Nordic driver and EUPATI Denmark, Board Vice-chair
- EURODIS Denmark
- Chair of the Malign Melanoma Patient organisation, Denmark, Board Vice-chair
- Patient representative in two HTA professional committees (malign melanoma as well as standardised treatment of cancer patients with venous thrombosis)
- Patient representative in the Danish Melanoma Database Steering Committee
- Board member of the Danish Institute for blind and weak sight people
- Patient representative in a Danish Medicines Agency stakeholder group developing recommendations for Decentralised Clinical Trials
- Patient Representative in the EATRISPlus PAC

Dinah Duarte

Prof. Ph.D

Dinah is in the Directorate for the Evaluation of Medicinal at INFARMED - National Authority of Medicines and Health Products in Portugal. Dinah is a pharmacist by education and has a MSc in “Regulatory Affairs and Evaluation of Medicinal Products” (Pharmacotoxicology field). Dinah is an Assistant Professor at Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon and Faculty of Sciences and Health Technologies, Lusófona University and expert member at the European Medicines Agency (EMA) since 2001. Next to her position as non-clinical assessor at Scientific Evaluation Unit, Directorate for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products, Portuguese Medicines Agency, INFARMED, I.P. she is also the Portuguese member at the Committee for Orphan Medicinal Products (COMP) of EMA; COMP Representative in the EMA’s group “Human Scientific Committees Working Party With Healthcare Professionals Organisations” and Member of the Portuguese scientific Evaluation Board of Medicines. Dinah is the former Head of Scientific Evaluation Unit (2011-2017) and Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) Portuguese member. As a specialist in “Regulatory Affairs” and “Hospital Pharmacy” by the Board of Specialists of the Portuguese Pharmaceutical Society (Ordem dos Farmacêuticos) she also took up the National Coordinator position of the Portuguese Hub at EATRIS-ERIC in 2018.

Maria Isabel Vieira

Ph.D

Isabel Vieira graduated in Pharmaceutical Sciences from the University of Lisbon and holds a PhD degree in Developmental Physiology and Functional Differentiation from the University Denis Diderot, in Paris. Later on, Isabel complemented her academic qualification with post-graduate research at the Center of Human Genetics, at the National Institute of Health, Lisbon. After joining in 2001, she currently works at INFARMED, having collaborated with the Pharmacovigilance and Clinical Trials Units. Since 2006, Isabel is a non-clinical pharmacotoxicological assessor at the Scientific Evaluation Unit. From 2008, she has been a member of the Safety Working Party at EMA, and joined the Committee for Advanced Therapies in 2020. Moreover, she has been Member of the Comissão de Avaliação de Medicamentos since 2013.

Antoine Brill

Prof. Ph.D

As Scientific Director Public Affairs, Antoine is overseeing the European public-private partnerships for the Servier Group and is advising the President of the group for European collaborative initiatives. With nearly thirty-five years of experience in Industry, his positions allowed him to carry out research projects that have led to several products in clinical development and now available to treat patients. Antoine has been in charge of managing and directing research as well as research and development activities in various companies ranging from Small and Medium Enterprises to Big Pharma.

From an academic point of view, Antoine followed a training in Pharmacy. He then obtained a PhD degree in pharmacology with an HDR and received a qualification for Professorship in both Pharmacology and Physiology. Antoine co-authored more than 100 scientific papers, and has more than 200 communications and invited lectures.

Antoine is Vice-Chair of the Research and Innovation Strategies group of the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) and member of the Innovation Board Sponsored Committee of EFPIA.

Umberto Restelli

Ph.D

Umberto Restelli holds a PhD in Integrated Business Management. He is adjunct professor of Health Systems Models at LIUC University (Italy) and is honorary senior lecturer at the School of Public Health, Faculty of Health Sciences of the Witwatersrand University, Johannesburg, South Africa. He collaborated and/or coordinated more than 60 research projects for clients such as the European Commission; the European Advanced Translational Research Infrastructure in Medicine; the World Health Organization; the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research; the Italian Ministry of Health; the Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs; hospital authorities; local health authorities; pharmaceutical companies. His main areas of expertise are Health Economics, Health Technology Assessment and Healthcare Management.

Maria do Céu Machado

Prof. Ph.D

Maria do Céu Machado is President of the Disciplinary Board of the College of Medicine, Professor of Pediatrics - Faculty of Medicine of the University of Lisbon, Member of the National Council for Ethics and Life Sciences, Vice-President of the Portuguese Academy of Medicine, Vice-President of the European Federation of the Academies of Medicine.

She was President of INFARMED (2017-19), High Commissioner for Health (2006-11), Clinical director of Centro Hospitalar Lisboa Norte (2013-14) e Hospital Fernando Fonseca (2005-06). Head of the Department of Pediatrics - Hospital Santa Maria, President of the National Committee for Children and Adolescent Health. She has degrees in Neonatology and Health Management.

8 research grants, 2 awards - Bial de Medicina Clínica (2002 e 2006), Quality Amélia de Mello (2005).

Published 172 papers, 8 books and 713 scientific lectures/ presentations.

Awarded with the Merit Order Grand Official by the President of the Portuguese Republic (2010), and Gold Medal by the Minister of Health (2012), Career Award by the Portuguese Society of Pediatrics (2018) and Merit Medal by ordem dos Médicos (2019).

If you have questions...

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